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Report on the FWF Open Access Journal Funding Initiative

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1. Introduction

This report presents the results of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) experimental initiative for funding high-quality Open Access journals in the social sciences and humanities.

After the completion of all eight projects that were funded in 2013, this report analyses the interim and final project reports¹ and highlights insights into Open Access journal funding.

2. Project Submission Phase and Funding Decision

In October 2012, the FWF in cooperation with the Federal Ministry of Science and Research (BWF) launched an initiative to provide start-up funding for innovative Open Access journals in the humanities and social sciences.² The initiative was aimed at media owners as defined in the Austrian Media Act ([Art. 1 Par. 1 No. 8](#)) and enabled applications both for the establishment of a new Open Access journal and for the flip of a subscription journal to Open Access. Existing Open Access journals were not allowed to apply for funding.

The objectives of the programme were to fund Open Access journals which were likely to gain high international renown and which had secured sustainable funding for the time beyond the initial funding period (36 months).

A total of approximately EUR 500,000 was available for the entire funding programme. Generally, the funding was limited to a maximum of EUR 50,000 per application. Initiatives which incorporated especially innovative elements could apply for as much as EUR 100,000.

In April 2013, 36 expressions of interest were submitted, of which the FWF Board invited the 19 most promising to submit a full proposal.

Some key data on the full proposals submitted:

1. Most of the journals were sponsored by research institutes such as universities, followed by learned societies and publishers.
2. 14 journals were new; five already existed as subscription journals and planned to switch to Open Access.
3. Seven journals could be attributed primarily to the social sciences and 12 to the humanities.
4. Only seven journals applied for more than EUR 50,000 and thus planned³ innovative elements for the journal.

¹ The analyses are based on aggregated data from all eight journals funded.

² See the first report, Reckling, F., & Scherag, E. (2012): Initial funding for high-quality Open Access journals in the humanities and social sciences. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16462>

³ In this context, innovations referred to measures which went beyond the standards of existing journals.

5. For the period after the three-year start-up financing, median costs were assumed to be approximately EUR 22,000 per year. Since about 20 articles were to be published per year, EUR 1,100 per article was calculated in the medium term.
6. For most of the journals, a long-term financing model was chosen based on support from the sponsoring institution or the media owner. A few journals were also supposed to be financed — at least in part — through the collection of article-processing charges.
7. All full proposals were evaluated by three international reviewers from a scholarly, technical and financial perspective.

According to the international reviewers and the FWF Board, the combination of scholarly quality, technical implementation and a sustainable financial basis was best exemplified by eight journals. This corresponded to an approval rate of 22%.

The following journals received funding by the FWF:

Journal	Media Owner
<u>APS – Austrian Journal of Political Science</u>	Austrian Association of Political Science (ÖGPW)
<u>Journal for Research Cultures (JRC)</u>	Research Institute for Arts and Technology
<u>medieval worlds. comparative & interdisciplinary Studies</u>	Institute for Medieval Research of the Austrian Academy of Sciences
<u>Musicologica Austriaca – Journal for Austrian Music Studies</u>	Austrian Musicological Society (ÖGMW)
<u>Region</u>	Vienna University of Economics and Business
<u>Translingual Discourse in Ethnomusicology (TDE)</u>	University of Vienna / University of Music and Performing Arts Graz
<u>transversal – Journal for Jewish Studies</u>	University of Graz
<u>TYCHE – Contributions to Ancient History. Papyrology and Epigraphy</u>	Verlag Holzhausen GmbH

3. Interim Evaluation

Half of each approved grant was paid out by the FWF at the beginning of the funding period in March 2014. The payment of the second half was made 18 months later, provided that (a) the journal was registered via ISSN and listed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and (b) a statement had been made to the FWF on how any of the reviewers' suggestions and recommendations had been successfully implemented so far or were planned to be implemented.

Depending on whether it was a transition to an Open Access journal or the creation of a new journal, the media owners had to master very different challenges.

Regarding the registration in DOAJ, the FWF Executive Board granted an extension of six months since most of the journals were not able to meet the criteria by the proposed deadline. However, all the journals had already obtained an International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) by then.

The following paragraphs outline some of the issues described in the statements:

One of the most frequently expressed criticisms of the new Open Access journals was the narrow or Eurocentric composition of the editorial board. Moreover, the new journals needed to develop strategies for attracting authors whereas the journals which already existed in print form had to convince the scientific community of the needed changes during the transition process.

In the initial phase of a journal, a top editorial board enhances the international visibility and reputation of the journal. International recognition can be a prerequisite for gaining a sufficient number of (high-profile) authors and referees. Neither young nor established, high-quality researchers are keen to submit papers to a new and unknown journal since there is a certain oversupply of journals and apart from that, scholars might be partly biased against the quality of new journals due to the fact that predatory publishers have generated negative publicity for Open Access journals.

Most of the media owners viewed the composition of the editorial board as a continuous process and had broadened the areas of specialization among its editorial board by this time.

For the existing print journals which planned to switch to Open Access, developing an international reputation was not a major issue, but they had to take adequate measures to simplify the transition for their authors. One journal reported having reservations about the commitment to the English language; furthermore, they feared that anglophone authors might therefore turn out to be dominant. As a result, they started financing proofreading for German-speaking authors.

Getting a new journal into major indexes is very challenging because most indexes require a minimum of five published journal articles, which can delay the process.

All the journals were planning to disseminate information about their journals and calls for papers as recommended by the reviewers through various channels including regular announcements in international list servers, subject-specific and bibliographic databases, Google Scholar, blogs, local libraries, etc.

Some of the journals reported that, depending on the hosts of the journal website, technical possibilities and innovations (download statistics, etc.) could not be fully exploited and implemented.

Electronic publication allows types of content not feasible for traditional journals such as the integration of video, audio, research data, etc., but it requires authors who are willing and/or able to use these possibilities to produce enhanced publication formats instead of traditional text-centric research publications.

To encourage the authors to take advantage of the range of options online publishing offers, one journal established an acceptance bonus for contributions that were particularly well prepared technically.

Almost all the journals planned to avoid APCs or submission fees and opted for a long-term funding model based on support from sponsors like research institutions or learned societies. In addition, some journals planned to minimize the costs and make use of volunteers or receive funding through advertising on the journal website.

In summary, most of the journals' goals stated in their applications were too ambitious, for instance, the number of articles planned for publication per year. Moreover, they underestimated the time that must be invested in the initial phase to establish the journal's internal procedures.

4. Analysis of the Final Project Reports

By the beginning of 2018, all eight final project reports had been submitted to the FWF. In the reports, the media owners were asked to answer technical questions as well as to report on their experiences during the whole project (see attachment for the final report document).

Based on the responses to the technical questions, the following results were found:

1. Most of the journals (4) published their articles semi-annually, two annually, one quarterly and one continuously.
2. Six journals carried out double-blind peer review and two journals open review.
3. The average time from submission to publication was 27.5 weeks, but this varied from journal to journal. Whereas some journals reported a period of 10 weeks, others mentioned an interval from 40 to 52 weeks.
4. In total, 481 articles were submitted to all the FWF-funded journals. Out of those 481 articles, 235 were accepted, resulting in an overall acceptance rate of 55%.

5. All journals published articles in English. Only two journals also accepted articles submitted in other languages than English.
6. Almost all journals used DOIs as the persistent identifier. One of the eight journals used another article identifier but will switch to DOIs soon.
7. All journals provided their articles as PDFs. Four of them provided additional HTML versions of their articles and one an XML version.
8. Four journals published their articles under the Creative Commons Attribution Licence CC BY. Two used the CC BY NC licence and the rest the CC BY NC ND licence.
9. Even though most journals did not operate on an APC basis, the media owners were still asked to estimate the average costs per article. On average, the costs per article were EUR 1,662.⁴ This is slightly above the average article-processing charges (APC) charged by commercial publishers (see [OpenAPC](#)). However, the costs in the initial phase of a journal are likely to be higher, and the APCs of commercial publishers always include the profit margins, too.

Apart from technical questions, the media owners were asked to describe the greatest obstacles or challenges they had to overcome during the project period. The following paragraph outlines the given responses in an aggregated way:

1. **Peer Review:** The peer review was more time-consuming and laborious than initially expected.
2. **Structural Problems:** The distribution of tasks among the editors and finding a notable editor was challenging.
3. **Submissions:** Since some of the journals were new, it was initially difficult to find contributors.
4. **Marketing:** Marketing and information activities had to be established.
5. **Indexing:** One media owner mentioned that the greatest challenge was to get indexed in DOAJ.

In addition, the PIs were asked to explain what future activities they were planning:

6. **Funding:** Almost all media owners mentioned the establishment of secure and sustainable funding streams for their journal.
7. **Structural Points:** Extending the editorial board and increasing the number of articles were mentioned as future steps.
8. **Marketing:** Marketing for the journal would be enhanced.
9. **Print:** One media owner reported that a print-on-demand service would be offered soon.

⁴ The real costs are likely to be slightly higher as the institutional overhead was not queried because it can vary greatly between institutions.

5. Conclusion

The media owners' responses have shown that publishing a journal can be challenging and the effort required must not be underestimated. Issues of a technical and organisational nature need to be taken into consideration before starting a journal, and additional knowledge must be gathered, such as in the field of marketing, which can provide, for example, a better understanding of strategies to attract authors for newly founded journals. In contrast to independent journals, legacy publishing houses have had decades to acquire this knowledge and establish functioning workflows, which they can use to develop efficient routines. Therefore, it is essential for media owners of independent journals to focus not only on the content they want to provide but also on the services needed to successfully establish their journals in the market.

One of the most pivotal points mentioned by almost all media owners in their final reports is funding. Keeping daily operations running requires a constant stream of financial support. The FWF programme provided an initial subsidy for Open Access journals; however, for a sustainable business model, other funding streams are necessary. Financial stability can, for example, be assured by research institutions or societies, as can be seen in the case of Tyche and the support by the University of Vienna or the Austrian Journal of Political Science and the Austrian Political Science Association (ÖGPW).

The programme was purposely conceived as an experiment in full awareness that the number of specialist journals likely to gain Open Access, on the one hand, and a high international reputation, on the other, is limited in a small research nation like Austria without large publishing houses. Furthermore, the experiment accepted the fact that not all journals would achieve the set goals in the long term.

It is still too early to draw a final conclusion. Therefore, approximately six years after the conversion or establishment of the journals, the FWF will conduct another survey of the journals.

Nevertheless, it is important to draw some general lessons from the programme, especially if the entire academic publishing market is to be prevented from coming under the control of just a few commercial publishers:

1. **Long-term Investments:** Research institutions, learned societies and funding organisations must devote a larger proportion of their budgets for academic publications to an independent, academia-governed publication infrastructure that provides long-term funding.
2. **Division of Labour:** Researchers must be able to concentrate on their core tasks, i.e. controlling quality and selecting the best publications. This also means that researchers need professional infrastructure and personnel support for the technical and administrative implementation.
3. **Economies of Scale:** Apart from some exceptions, a certain critical mass is crucial to be able to work cost-effectively. This means that the technical and administrative infrastructures should be used by more than one publication venue.

4. **Pooling of Resources:** Since not every research institution, learned society or funding agency can meet the above conditions, it will be necessary to form national and international consortia to ensure an independent and open publication infrastructure including effective cost sharing.

The FWF has tried to implement these learnings and, in recent years, to invest primarily with national and international partners in Open Access infrastructures. These include Europe PubMed Central, OAPEN Library, Open Library of Humanities, SciPost, Directory of Open Access Journals or arXiv. The Plan S initiative of European funding organisations will further intensify this development.

6. Attachments

GUIDELINES FOR FINAL REPORTS ON FWF-FUNDED PROJECTS

The full report must be submitted via e-mail in WORD or PDF format to eva.scherag@fwf.ac.at AND falk.reckling@fwf.ac.at with the subject OAJ – XX

Part I

The project summaries (in German and English) are intended for interested members of the public and should be presented in a manner which is intelligible to non-expert audiences.

Target audience: **general public**

Parts II & III

These should provide all the information requested. They are **to be written in English** in 11 pt font, line spacing 1.5. The **total length** must not exceed 10,000 characters (without spaces: approx. four DIN A4 pages). **No annexes** are permitted.

The data included in **Part II** will be recorded by the FWF for statistical purposes and published in aggregate form only (i.e., not at the individual level).

Target audience: **peer reviewers**

Part IV

This provides grant recipients with an opportunity to report on their interactions with the FWF's administrative staff in the course of the project.

Target audience: **FWF**

OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL FINAL REPORT

Project number	
Journal title	
Journal acronym	
Journal website	
ISSN/eISSN	
Link to DOAJ entry	
Media owner	
Publisher	
Contact person	

Summary for public relations purposes

The project's most significant results (scientific advances) from the media owner's point of view should be presented on a single page (DIN A4, 11 pt font, line spacing 1.5) in a way that is comprehensible to the general public. In this summary, it is important to use as few technical terms as possible in order to ensure that the text is interesting and understandable for people who are not familiar with the field. The main point should be mentioned at the very start of the summary. Descriptions of the issues addressed and results obtained should be short and succinct. Possible applications to or implications for social, cultural, ecological, medical, economic or technological areas should also be mentioned briefly.

The summary should be submitted in both **German** and **English** (with the following headings). All summaries will be made available in the FWF's online project database. The FWF will not edit the summaries, meaning that the authors bear full responsibility for the content of these texts.

1. **Zusammenfassung für die Öffentlichkeitsarbeit**
2. **Summary for public relations purposes**

Data on the journal

How frequently are the articles published?

Continuously Monthly Quarterly Semi-annually Annually Other (please specify)

What kind of peer review is usually carried out?

Single-blind review Double-blind review Open review Other (please specify)

Average time from submission to publication: weeks

Overall manuscript acceptance rate since establishment of journal

	From dd.mm.yyyy to dd.mm.yyyy
Number of articles submitted	
Number of articles accepted	
Acceptance rate (%)	

Language of published articles

	%
English	
German	
Other languages	
Total	100

Affiliation countries of corresponding authors

	No.	%
Austria		
Germany/Switzerland		
Europe		
USA/Canada		
Others		
Total		100

Licences for re-use of articles

	No.	%
CC BY		
CC BY – SA		
CC BY – NC		
CC BY – NC – ND		
Other licences		
No specific licence		
Total		100

Which article identifiers does the journal use?

DOI Handle Other None

Which full-text formats are available?

PDF HTML XML ePub Other (please specify)

Average cost per published article (in EUR):

Estimated cost per item:⁵

Cost items	EUR	%
Staff and outsourcing		
Online system		
Article processing		
Features		
Dissemination/marketing		
Total expenditure		100

⁵ **Staff and outsourcing:** Staff directly involved in handling submissions and published articles, and in supporting outsourced providers. **Online systems:** Cost of operating third-party systems that process submissions and published articles. **Article processing:** Other publishing costs, including management of editorial and article-processing teams, and routine maintenance of online systems. **Features:** All costs of non-research-article material on the article's website, such as insight articles, editorials, feature articles and podcasts. **Dissemination/marketing:** All dissemination and marketing activities, including costs related to indexing and promoting the journal and its content, as well as mission-related communication and advocacy (see [elifesciences: <https://elifesciences.org/elifesciences-news/inside-elifesciences-what-it-costs-publish>](https://elifesciences.org/elifesciences-news/inside-elifesciences-what-it-costs-publish)).

III. Brief project report

- *To be written in English in 11 pt font, line spacing 1.5*
- *All information requested to be provided.*
- **Length** *not to exceed 10,000 characters in total (without spaces, approx. 4 DIN A4 pages)*

Target audience: **peer reviewers**

- 1. Key facts about the new journal: Most important results/achievements and brief description of their significance**
(e.g. indexing, dissemination, quality assurance, long-term archiving)
- 2. What were/are the greatest obstacles/challenges to be overcome in the project?**
- 3. What activities are planned for the future?**
(e.g. dissemination strategies, sustainable funding/business models, innovations)
- 4. Your project received extra funding for special innovations. Please describe the innovations implemented / measures taken that go beyond the standards of existing journals.**